

Highlights

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A post-Communist path dependence: Providing evidence for a difference in the demand for populism in CEE and the West

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ABSTRACT

The CEE public has the lowest degree of institutional trust in the EU, is sceptical towards democracy, and expresses greater openness to welfarism yet not to gender equality. These attitudes are frequently justified by the legacies of Communism and the transition. Taking these as a starting point, the article presents evidence for a difference in demand for populism between the West and the CEE, with the following findings. Populist voters in the CEE trust their political representatives, and participate in political rallies, yet tend not to follow political news outlets. Anti-immigration sentiment is less determinant, while a pro-welfarist stance has a stronger influence on the populist vote in the CEE than in the West. Therefore, in contrast to the post-austerity, reactionary nature of populism in the West, populism in the CEE is more solidified due to the legacies of Communism.

1. Introduction

There is a growing body of work dealing with how post-Communist legacies affect voter preferences (Minkenberg et al., 2002; Pytlas, 2015; Stanley, 2017). For instance, Pop-Eleches and Tucker (2017) evidenced that against the global average post-Communist societies are (1) less favourable towards democracy, (2) on average more conservative, and (3) exhibit greater support for welfare policies but not gender equality. Regarding welfare expectations, Stan (2015) identified a collective longing for a more abundant provision of welfare, a sentiment that some would refer to as post-Communist nostalgia (Todorova, 2005). We may therefore argue that a sense of socio-economic uncertainty had reinstated (Daigle, Neulen and Hofeman, 2018) the demand for increased state interventionism, which by Dornbusch and Edwards (1990) is referred to as economic populism.

On the other hand, there is also an expectation for the impact of the transition to leave a lasting mark on the region (Bunce et al., 2005). Individual level indicators provide a certain foundation for this argument, as the Life in Transition Surveys respondents are found to have (1) mixed feelings about the outcome of the transition, (2) a significant deterioration of the perception of corruption relative to the pre-transition years, and a rather (3) sceptical attitude to democracy (EBRD, 2020). The misalignment between a promise of Return to Europe (Sztompka, 1999) and the post-transition reality led some scholars to believe that the post-Communist societies have had a delay in realising the overall socio-economic cost of the process – an argument referred to as the post-transitional fatigue (Totev and Kubik, 2017; Berend and Berend, 2009). These, as I argue in the paper, alter the optics used by populist parties in the CEE and are signalled by a slightly different nature of the demand for populism in the

region. For instance, in the CEE the anti-gender sentiment is understood as a marker of national identity (Kemper, 2016). Scapegoating of minorities in the CEE is oftentimes taken out of the typical political right-left placement, presented as an anti-Western slogan and a threat to national belonging. As noted by Grzebalska and Pető (2018), sexual minorities rights are often discredited as coming from: evils from the West, that steal our children, who are enemies of the traditional national identity of a Christian family. Another differentiating trait is the altered nature of political participation. Namely, the CEEs audiences are found to have a lower degree of overall trust in media credibility (Castro-Herrero, Hopmann and Engesser, 2016), to have a greater disregard for the entirety of the industry, and to frequently discredit private media outlets as foreign influence or corrupt elitism (Stetka, 2012). This distrust is a heritage of the Communist times when the public became accustomed to biased media, entirely subordinated to the state (Castro-Herrero et al., 2016). Furthermore, up until the fall of the Berlin wall the CEE publics found themselves on the us-vs-the-state divide which resulted in a unifying component of an anti-Communist mentalité populaire Mandrou (1985); Herspring (1992). The anti-communist sentiment was fundamental for building up the collective liberation spirit leading up to the 1989 revolts Berend (2005). And while in the West we would expect a pro-socialist activation in the political processes, such activation is deformed in the CEE, a region which for long had opposed a coercive power of the state (Todosijević and Enyedi, 2008). It should be noted, however, that the socioeconomic as well as political contexts of the countries in question are far from uniform. For the CEE, the post-Communist heritage, as well as the experience of the transition, greatly varied. From a shock-therapy in Poland, goulash communism in Hungary, and rapid reforms in secular Czechoslovakia, to healing of the ethno-nationalist, post-dictatorial wounds in Romania. Similarly for the West, there is a great degree of heterogeneity across the region with different socioeconomic and political trajectories. However,

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as this article is concerned with a regional comparison, we may agree that the West and the CEE are delineated by the experience of the Communist rule and the 1990s transition. We may follow Sztompka (2004) understanding of the CEEs experience of Communism and the transition as a collective social trauma that unified the CEE and framed its democratic consolidation (Sztompka, 2004, p.171). This article argues that the nature of the populist offer in the CEE is influenced by these legacies. Populist parties use a re-occurring contextual narrative, blending anti-establishment and anti-elitism with the post-transition, the socio-economic divide between the us, the ordinary people against them, the liberal, corrupt elites (Berend, 2005, p.197). This bipolarity is highly reminiscent of the post-Communist us-vs-the-state divisionism that mobilised the protest movements leading up to the transition. In that light, this article seeks to answer the following questions: Is there a difference between the demand for populism in Central and Eastern Europe versus the West? If yes, what are specific attitudes differentiating the nature of the demand for populism in the region? And lastly, are these differentiating attitudes potentially explained by the legacy of Communism and the transition? As we are dealing here with the questions of attitudes, the required method will use individual-level data as I explain in the following section.

2. Data

Given the nature of the research, the study incorporates individual-level data from the ESS survey, on an aggregated level starting from 2002 until 2018 (ESS, 2002-2018). The descriptive statistics of the model controls are summarised in Table 1. Respondents are anonymized, and by design non-repetitive which assures the independence of observations across the data collection points. The region coded as the West includes: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. Countries coded as the CEE include all the post-Communist states that successfully joined the European Union i.e.: Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, and Slovenia. Naturally, there is a great degree of heterogeneity across the sample. Therefore, the article examines the average impact of the Communist legacies in the sample, capturing the time-invariant components by country-fixed effects.

Table 1 here

The dependent variable, the populist vote, is binary, coded 1 for populist voting and 0 for non-populist voting based on the Rooduijn, de Lange and van der Brug (2011) classification. There is an expected degree of missing observations (23.21%), which includes abstentions, ineligible votes, as well as non-responses. The logistic regression also includes new items argued to be sourced in the post-Communist past of the region, which differentiate the CEEs

electorate from the West, i.e.: political participation and exposure to political news. In such a way, the research question departs from considerations by (Algan, Guriev, Papaioannou and Passari, 2017; Guiso, Herrera, Morelli, Sonno et al., 2017; Inglehart and Catterberg, 2002).

3. Methodology

Firstly, the study explores correlations using exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and provides a preliminary check for the existence of a regional difference in demand for populism with the results of a two-tail difference-in-means test. Subsequently, the study identifies the existence of regional variability in populist vote using the Oaxaca decomposition (Sinning, Hahn and Bauer, 2008). The Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition allows showing how the vector of explanatory variables influences the by-group difference. The decomposition verifies which part of the identified difference in the dependent variable is attributable to the observable characteristics of each defined group (that is, explanatory variables of the model endowments E) and which is due to behavioural characteristics (i.e. model coefficients C). A twofold decomposition equation is (Sinning et al., 2008):

$$\bar{Y}_A - \bar{Y}_B = (\bar{X}_A - \bar{X}_B)\beta_B + \bar{X}_B(\beta_A - \beta_B) = E + C \quad (1)$$

Where the difference in the vector of response variables of the reference category (X_A), here being the CEE, is weighted by the coefficients of the baseline category, here the West (X_B). That is, the difference in the level of the outcome variable ($\Delta\bar{Y} = \bar{Y}_A - \bar{Y}_B$) for the baseline group (the West) is being converged as it was to approximate the mean outcome of the reference group (the CEE). Hence, the second step of the two-fold procedure is to estimate the portion of the baseline groups mean change in the outcome variable using the reference group coefficients as the weighting vector (Etezady, Shaw, Mokhtarian and Circella, 2021).

The third step allows us a comparison of determinants across the regions. For that I use a logistic regression on the populist vote, allowing me to present the predictive marginal change in attitudes influencing the dependent variable. The estimated logistic regression equation (2) is as follows:

$$Pr(Y_{ij}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{ij} + \beta_2 Z_{ij} + \beta_3 Z_{ij} * CEE + f_j + f_t + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Where the probability to vote for a populist party $Pr(Y_{ij})$ is estimated using a vector of socio-demographic controls $\beta_1 X_{ij}$ of a respondent (i) across countries (j). The model also estimates several linear combinations of survey variables ($\beta_2 Z_{ij}$) referred to as dimensions and the interaction term ($\beta_3 Z_{ij} * CEE$) which allows us to see the regional difference in attitudes. Due to the unobserved heterogeneity between the waves and countries, the model includes fixed country effects (f_j) and fixed time effects (f_t). The (ϵ_{ij}) denotes a random error term.

4. Analysis

EFA confirmed the aggregation on authoritarian, anti-immigration and trust items as previously suggested by Algan et al. (2017); Inglehart and Catterberg (2002); Guiso et al. (2017). Altogether, the analysis retained six factors with satisfactory eigenvalues. The oblique rotation confirmed a negligible inter-factor correlation warranting further examination using an orthogonal varimax rotation. That allows for assuming independence between the explanatory variables of the model.

Table 2 here

The regional comparison of the standardised means (the first two rows of Table 3) shows a positive standard deviation difference for the CEE in authoritarian openness, economic insecurity and unfavourable attitude to sexual minorities which suggests the region is indeed more conservative and pro-welfarist than the sample average what supports the theorised associations.

Table 3 here

Subsequently, I verify whether there is a statistically significant difference between the means of the populist vote in the examined regions. The two-tail difference in the means test shows that on average respondents in the CEE are slightly more favourable towards populist parties than individuals in the West. This positive difference shown in Table 4 (0.013) invites further identification of the source of this existing variability.

Table 4 here

The aggregated results of the decomposition identified a statistically significant difference between CEE (group X_A) and the West (group X_B) as shown in Table 5. The overall difference in estimated probabilities of the outcome variable between the groups (Raw) is 0.0371 (positive and statistically significant). We notice a smaller change in endowments, estimated on the CEE with the West's vector of explanatory variables, than in the coefficients - these being a proportion of change in the mean outcome for the West had it had the CEE's coefficients holding its endowments constant. That implies that the difference in populist voting between the CEE and West is explained less by how different voters are along the dimensions considered in our regression (variables entering the specification) and more by how these characteristics convert into the dependent variable, i.e., populist voting in the two groups. The considerably larger sample size of the West results in a slightly more statistically significant result (p -value=0.0015) than is the case for CEE.

Table 5 here

Lastly, both coefficients and endowments signs are positive which suggests that these vectors contribute to a larger overall difference expressed in the final difference of means. The approximated standard error suggests the results are

statistically significant, however, given the degree of approximation (bootstrapping) these should be treated with caution (Sinning et al., 2008; Jann, 2008). Having presented a considerable amount of evidence for a positive difference in means of the populist vote between the CEE and the West I proceed with the final model.

5. Findings

The results for the whole sample replicate what was theorised as determinants of demand for populism in the West (Algan et al., 2017; Inglehart and Catterberg, 2002; Guiso et al., 2017) for a white, less educated, older male to be the most likely to vote for a populist party (Control model). Secondly, the populist vote is positively affected by openness to authoritarian values (Authoritarian openness, a sense of threat coming from immigration and those affected by economic circumstances. Also as in previous empirical studies, the model identified those with a lower degree of trust in politics as more likely to vote for a populist party.

Table 6 here

Thirdly, aligned with theoretical expectations, the Dimensions model suggests that respondents in favour of governments tackling income inequality are equally more likely to vote for a populist party, while individuals with more openness towards sexual freedoms are less likely to vote for a populist party in Europe. The coefficient on exposure to news is not uniformly statistically significant across the models, which makes this finding rather cautionary, however, as such, it indicates that Europeans interested in political affairs are equally more likely to vote for a populist party. For political participation, interestingly, the coefficient is negative and statistically significant across the models, indicating those individuals who are engaged in political participation are less likely to vote for the populist party across Europe.

Let's examine these differences more closely. Firstly, the CEEs support for populist parties is most frequent among villagers. Secondly, populist voters in the CEE are relatively more unfavourable towards sexual minorities than populist voters in the West, which aligns with the theorised expectation for the CEE to be more conservative

Figure 1 here

Figure 2 here

Figure 3 here

Figure 4 here

Thirdly, on average individuals in both regions expect a government to reduce income inequality with a higher predictive marginal probability for populist voters in the CEE. Considering the anti-immigration aspects, the coefficient suggests that individuals hostile towards migrants are more likely to vote for populist parties, however, this probability is marginally higher for Western European countries. Interestingly, the difference between the political trust across the regions is considerable. We would expect a lower degree of political trust to positively influence the populist vote, which

is the confirmed finding for the whole sample (Dimensions model). However, the CEE interaction term is positive and statistically significant, indicating a reverse association. That is, respondents in the CEE who have a higher degree of political trust are strongly more likely to vote for a populist party. With regards to the exposure to news outlets (Figure 4), the model found a small, yet, statistically significant difference between the CEE and the West. Respondents from the CEE region are more likely to vote for a populist party if their interest in politics is reduced. Lastly, concerning political participation, the model identified that individuals involved in some form of political engagement are more likely to vote for a populist party.

6. Discussion and further research

Certain electoral attitudes towards populist parties are seemingly repetitive across the regions, namely an older, less educated, prone to authoritarianism, white male is highly likely to vote for a populist party. However, insightful differences were also unearthed, which I discuss in more detail below. Firstly, the anti-immigration sentiments have a more dynamic influence over the populist vote in the West, with rather a static trend in the CEE. We may reason that compared to the West; the CEE had a smaller exposure to the influx of immigration in the recent decade which would explain that result. From the post-Communist legacy perspective, we could argue that the anti-immigration sentiments in the CEE were long subdued, and are in general argued to have an ethnonational foundation (Tismaneanu, 1998; Mole, 2016) rather than an anti-globalisation character. In the West, anti-immigration sentiments will be characteristically reactionary to the current socioeconomic tensions, while in the CEE we may argue these claims are more static and go back to the post-Communist, protest-activating us-vs-the-state divide. Secondly, individuals with a preference for government to tackle income inequality are more likely to vote for a populist party across the sample, however, this probability is slightly higher in the case of the CEE (Figure 2). That result reinstates the argument put forward by Pop-Eleches and Tucker (2017), who also identified CEE as a region scoring higher on welfarist expectations than the global average. From the post-Communist legacy perspective, I would argue that the current populist offer with strong pro-welfarist components mobilises the electorate that longs for the better old times where all were equal Boyer (2010). That association seems particularly strong in the case of Hungary (Benczes, 2016) and Poland (Toplišek, 2020).

Yet, the most striking finding is on political trust and satisfaction with governance. In the CEE, respondents with a higher degree of political trust are on average more likely to vote for a populist party, while in the West, voters distrusting politics are more likely to vote for populist parties (Inglehart and Norris, 2016). We should analyse this result in the context of post-Communist legacies. Firstly, post-Communist countries struggle with a chronically low degree of political trust. Low political trust results in relatively

low turnouts when compared to Western democracies. Post-Communist electorates are also found to be sceptical of the idea of democracy, which in principle makes them disinterested in the electoral process. That leads us to the second consideration - electoral absenteeism. From the research on the West, we expect individuals disbelieving to attain political change to dissociate themselves from politics and cease to participate in electoral cycles altogether, which may indirectly inflate the populist vote share (Guiso et al., 2017). For the CEE, this disengagement has an element of continuity, as the general public became disenchanting with the transition. Therefore, in the CEE there is a generally smaller number of active voters, and hence electoral support around anti-political-establishment populist parties in the region.

That argument is further supported by the finding on political participation. Political participation turned out to be a significant factor influencing the populist vote in both regions. In the West, those less active in political circles are more likely to vote for a populist party, while in the CEE this relationship is reversed. We may justify this difference through the lens of the post-Communist legacy. The Communist regime made the CEE public accustomed to an imbalanced coercive relationship with the state, and thus the CEE public was adept in forming clandestine circles of influence with an anti-state, counter-hegemonic attitude to authority. Individuals were not able to openly vent their discontent through legal protests or civil society organisations (Ekiert and Kubik, 2001). The anti-state component of populist narration is thus successful in attracting politically active individuals that attend rallies and participate in campaigns. In the West, political participation for long embodied the gist of bottom-up, democratic oversight, with a more dominant role of civic society organisations rather than informal circles of influence that predominantly took over the role of civil society during Communism in the CEE. When combined with general scepticism of democracy, the demand for populism in the region has a solidified, post-Communist fundament.

That leads us to the finding on the exposure to political news outlets. In the West, individuals actively following political news are found to be more likely to vote for a populist party. This association is not evidenced in the CEE, where individuals less interested in political news are identified as more likely to vote for a populist party. Admittedly, the Communist legacy on media ownership had a detrimental effect on trust in media credibility. Individuals with a particularly low degree of interest in the media are therefore more likely to vote for populist parties, which portray news outlets as corrupt, foreign influence (Stetka, 2012). Combined with the discussed finding on political participation, political trust, and a strong preference for welfarism, this result complements the overall picture of a populist voter in the CEE. The avenues for further research are broad. The results on a regional level, as identified here, invite a country study to be able to get an in-depth outlook on these regional contextualities. Such contribution would

be particularly insightful considering the items examined by this article, namely the surprising finding on political trust, exposure to news outlets and political participation. Moreover, it seems useful to further explore the regions country-specific populist features, particularly the role of communal circles of influence instance Catholic Church in Poland, authoritarian kleptocracy in Hungary, or technocratic populists in Czechia. These constitute examples of tie-knot kinship networks that are argued to remain influential in the current political scene. These aspects constitute a useful lens to examine how post-Communist legacy blends in with the sense of anti-state bipolarity, which is argued to be the primary solidifier of the populist vote in the CEE.

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